

PREPARATION AND ELECTROCHEMICAL PERFORMANCE OF TUBULAR $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ /CARBON COMPOSITE ANODE

H. Choi, J. Im, C.R. Park*

Carbon Nanomaterials Design Laboratory, Global Research Laboratory, Research Institute of Advanced Materials, and Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul 151-744, Korea

* Corresponding author (crpark@snu.ac.kr)

Keywords: $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ /Carbon composite, Hybrid Capacitor, Lithium Ion Battery, Supercapacitor

1. Introduction

As the demand for hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) and electric vehicles (EVs) as an environmentally friendly transportation is ever increasing, high performance energy storage devices viz. with high energy density and high power density with cycle stability simultaneously, become extremely important [1-3]. However, neither lithium ion rechargeable battery (LIB) nor supercapacitor, which is representative electrochemical energy storage devices in these days, can meet the practically required performances [1-3]. It is thus quite natural to conceive to make a new energy device based on a fusion of the concept of LIB that can generate high energy density and supercapacitor that has high power density. In recent years, there has been a great interest for design the battery-supercapacitor hybrid energy device, which may be called hybrid capacitor [4-6], to combine these two different kinds of devices through asymmetric electrode system.

Basically, the asymmetric electrode system consists of the negative electrode using Li ion intercalation material and the positive electrode indicating electrochemical double layer capacitance (EDLC) within an organic solvent dissolving lithium salt due to higher available potential range compared with aqueous solution electrolyte [7-10]. In the case of negative electrode that can provide high energy density in the hybrid energy storage device, fast charge/discharge capability with long term cycle stability in the Li ion intercalation process to balance with positive electrode [7,8,10]. Carbonaceous materials which have been widely used as the anode in the LIBs can be used as the Li ion intercalation negative electrode in hybrid capacitor due to high energy density and good cycle stability [11]. However, it is difficult to maintain the capacitance

in the high rate circumstance, because of poor Li ion transfer kinetics from lithiation mechanism in the carbonaceous materials. On the other hand, $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and TiO_2 based materials have been reported as candidate materials for negative electrode in hybrid capacitor due to fast charge/discharge capability without volume expansion causing great cycle stability [12]. Improving very low electrical conductivity (about 10^{-12} S/cm) and increasing specific capacity for Li ion of $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and TiO_2 based materials will make the breakthrough in the negative electrode of the hybrid energy storage device, hybrid capacitor.

Therefore, it is aimed in this work at developing a high rate capability negative electrode material with morphology control and material hybridization to find the clue for hybrid capacitor. We prepared $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ /Carbon hybrid composite nanotube (denoted LTO/C-HCN) through electrospinning, hydrothermal reaction, and heat treatment. 1D-shaped tubular structure and LTO/C hybridization can provide the fast charge transfer kinetics indicating the fast charge/discharge property. LTO/C-HCNs were characterized and tested using various analytic methods and electrochemical performance test methods.

2 Experimental

LTO/C-HCN series samples were prepared through electrospinning followed by hydrothermal reaction and heat treatments at a specified temperature. Typically, aqueous polyvinylalcohol (PVA) solution was electrospun into a bath containing ethanol/titanium terta-isopropoxide (TIPP) solution to obtain TiO_2 layer on the surface of the electrospun PVA nanofibers via in situ sol-gel reaction. PVA/ TiO_2 -core/shell nanofibers were subjected to

hydrothermal reaction at 120 °C for 12 hrs to obtain LTO/PVA nanofibers. After filtering and washing, the product was vacuum dried for 6hrs, then heat treated in the N₂ atmosphere at 800 °C for 3 hrs. Prepared samples were characterized by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, SDT Q600, TA), X-ray diffractometry (XRD, D8 advance, Bruker), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JSM-6700F, JEOL), and high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM, F20, Tecnai). The electrochemical performances of the LTO/C-HCN were examined with a galvanostatic cell cycler (WBCS3000, WonATech) at various charge/discharge rates.

3 Results and Discussion

Morphologies of the LTO/C-HCN sample were examined using FE-SEM (Figure 1) and HR-TEM (Figure 2). The samples have a well-developed tubular structure due to a burn-off of PVA during heat treatment. In the case of the LTO/C-HCN, it was clear from HR-TEM images in Figure 2 that the sample is composed of typical porous carbons and well developed Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ crystalline phase. Especially, oxygen and titanium-containing groups in the TiO₂ layer on the electrospun PVA nanofibers can be act as the carbon-activation catalyst during the heat treatment process. Also, 1D-tubular structure of the sample is confirmed, which is in a good agreement with the result of FE-SEM analysis. These morphological and microstructural features are expected to enhance the electron and Li ion transportation kinetics in the electrochemical reaction with introduction of effective electron pathway and also to create additional capacitance of the porous carbonaceous material from carbonization of electrospun PVA.

Fig. 1. Typical FE-SEM micrograph of the LTO/C-HCN sample.

Fig. 2. Typical HR-TEM micrographs of the LTO/C-HCN sample. (A:low-magnification image, B:high-magnification image)

Figure 3 displays the N₂ sorption isotherm and pore size distribution of the LTO/C-HCN sample. The BET surface area and pore volume are calculated to be 161.52 m²/g and 0.21 cm³/g, respectively, which are relatively higher values compared with typical Li₄Ti₅O₁₂. Also, mean pore size is calculated to be 5.23 nm, which indicates that mainly formed pores after heat treatment are in the range of mesopore. The porosity results of the LTO/C-HCN give a good evidence of well-developed 1D-tubular structure with porous carbon by catalytic effect of TiO₂ layer. Moreover, porous carbon phase can give the additional EDLC to the pseudocapacitance from Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ phase, which indicates the possibility of the LTO/C-HCN as the negative electrode for the hybrid capacitor.

Fig. 3. Nitrogen sorption isotherm and pore size distribution (inset) of LTO/C-HCN sample.

The XRD pattern as shown in Figure 4 is also one of the good evidence for the successful formation of the LTO/carbon hybrid composite. Most of diffraction peaks are well correspond to the XRD patterns of typical $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ in JCPDF card No. 49-0207. However, it also indicates that there exists a small amount of TiO_2 together with LTO. The scattering profile of carbon phase in the composite is basically that of amorphous carbon due to low heat treatment temperature, and hence swamped by very strong diffraction intensity of the crystalline LTO phase.

TGA of the LTO/C-HCN was figured out to calculate the mass ratio of each component in Figure 5. Most of carbonaceous materials are decomposed from 300 to 400 °C in the air atmosphere. The mass ratio of the $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ phase and carbonaceous materials in the composite after heat treatment are 78 wt% and 22 wt%, respectively.

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of the LTO/C-HCN.

Fig. 5. TGA result of the LTO/C-HCN to 800 °C with 5 °C/min of heating rate in the air atmosphere.

The electrochemical behaviors of the LTO/C-HCN sample were tested at various charge/discharge rates from 100 mA/g to 2000 mA/g in the potential range of 1~2.5 V vs. Li/Li^+ to figure out the possibility as the negative electrode for hybrid capacitor. Anodic performance of the LTO/C-HCN is indicated in Figure 6 with a plot for discharge capacity retention at each charge/discharge rates. Reversible specific capacities of the sample are about 121, 115, 98, and 82 mAh/g at 100, 500, 1000, and 2000 mA/g of charge/discharge rates, respectively, with good cycle stability during 20 cycles per each step. At 100 mA/g of relatively low charge/discharge rate, reversible specific capacity is smaller than the theoretical value of typical $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ due to the 78 wt% of $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ phase in the LTO/C-HCN phase in the TGA analysis (Figure 5). With increase of charge/discharge rates, carbonaceous material in the composite, which is not electrochemical-active in the 1~2.5 V of potential range, enhances the electrochemical performance at high rates compared with typical $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ phase [11,13,14]. Inset plot in Figure 6 for discharge capacity retention at each charge/discharge rates also displays that LTO/C-HCN has better high rate capability than typical $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ phase as anode material.

Fig. 6. Anodic performances of the LTO/C-HCN at various charge/discharge rates. Inset indicates discharge capacity retention at each charge/discharge rates.

Anodic performance tests at various charge/discharge rates show that LTO/C-HCN can be used as the high rate rechargeable LIB electrode

material, because fast charge/discharge rate capability and high surface area cause high energy density at high power density. Therefore, morphological control with 1D-shaped tubular structure and hybridization of $\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and activated carbonaceous material are effective on fast charge/discharge property due to improved charge transfer kinetics.

4 Conclusions

LTO/C-HCN was successfully synthesized using electrospinning method followed by hydrothermal reaction and heat treatment. Especially, tubular structure and activated carbon phase in the LTO/C-HCN enhance the charge transfer kinetics via faster electron and ion transportation, which was confirmed in the electrochemical test at various charge/discharge rates. Also, LTO/C-HCN can give the clue of the hybrid capacitor for electrical vehicles which require high energy capacity with high power density.

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Ministry of Knowledge Economy (MKE) of Korea through the Research Institute of Advanced Materials (RIAM) and Global Research Laboratory (GRL) program, and the Research Institute of Industrial Science & Technology (RIST) Fund 0592-20100006.

References

- [1] A. S. Arico, P. Bruce, B. Scrosati, J. M. Tarascon and W. Van Schalkwijk "Nanostructured materials for advanced energy conversion and storage devices". *Nature Materials*, Vol. 4, No. 5, pp 366-377, 2005.
- [2] H. Li, Z. Wang, L. Chen and X. Huang "Research on Advanced Materials for Li-ion Batteries". *Advanced Materials*, Vol. 21, No. 45, pp 4593-4607, 2009.
- [3] J. B. Goodenough and Y. Kim "Challenges for Rechargeable Li Batteries†". *Chemistry of Materials*, Vol. 22, No. 3, pp 587-603, 2009.
- [4] A. D. Pasquier, I. Plitz, J. Gural, S. Menocal and G. Amatucci "Characteristics and performance of 500 F asymmetric hybrid advanced supercapacitor prototypes". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 113, No. 1, pp 62-71, 2003.
- [5] A. D. Pasquier, I. Plitz, J. Gural, S. Menocal and G. Amatucci "Power-ion battery: bridging the gap between Li-ion and supercapacitor chemistries". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 136, No. 1, pp 160-170, 2004.
- [6] V. L. Pushparaj, M. M. Shaijumon, A. Kumar, S. Murugesan, L. Ci, R. Vajtai, R. J. Linhardt, O. Nalamasu and P. M. Ajayan "Flexible energy storage devices based on nanocomposite paper". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, Vol. 104, No. 34, pp 13574-13577, 2007.
- [7] G. G. Amatucci, F. Badway, A. D. Pasquier and T. Zheng "An Asymmetric Hybrid Nonaqueous Energy Storage Cell". *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, Vol. 148, No. 8, pp A930-A939, 2001.
- [8] M. Mastragostino and F. Soavi "Strategies for high-performance supercapacitors for HEV". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 174, No. 1, pp 89-93, 2007.
- [9] S. Nohara, A. A. Toshihide, H. Wada, N. Furukawa, H. Inoue, N. Sugoh, H. Iwasaki and C. Iwakura "Hybrid capacitor with activated carbon electrode, $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ electrode and polymer hydrogel electrolyte". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 157, No. 1, pp 605-609, 2006.
- [10] A. D. Pasquier, I. Plitz, S. Menocal and G. Amatucci "A comparative study of Li-ion battery, supercapacitor and nonaqueous asymmetric hybrid devices for automotive applications". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 115, No. 1, pp 171-178, 2003.
- [11] T. Brousse, R. Marchand, P. L. Taberna and P. Simon "TiO₂ (B)/activated carbon non-aqueous hybrid system for energy storage". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 158, No. 1, pp 571-577, 2006.
- [12] V. Khomenko, E. Raymundo-Piñero and F. Béguin "High-energy density graphite/AC capacitor in organic electrolyte". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 177, No. 2, pp 643-651, 2008.
- [13] X. Hu, Z. Deng, J. Suo and Z. Pan "A high rate, high capacity and long life (LiMn₂O₄ + AC)/Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ hybrid battery-supercapacitor". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 187, No. 2, pp 635-639, 2009.
- [14] K. Naoi, S. Ishimoto, Y. Isobe and S. Aoyagi "High-rate nano-crystalline Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ attached on carbon nano-fibers for hybrid supercapacitors". *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 195, No. 18, pp 6250-6254, 2010.